
SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL IMPORTANCE OF THE STYLE OF PHILOSOPHICAL THINKING

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KEYWORDS

thinking, thought, reasoning,
mental cognition, structure,
essence, being, nature, society,
logic, mentality, epistemology,
selective, verbal, prediction

ABSTRACT

Today, as a result of the process of globalization covering the earth, drastic changes are taking place in the consciousness and thinking of mankind. In particular, various mental influences on the way of thinking are increasing. The importance of scientific thinking is incomparable for the understanding of the world, the comprehensive understanding of the laws of life and society, and the worldview of different peoples and nations on earth. In a word, arming our youth with scientific thinking is the need of the hour.

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ФАЛСАФИЙ ТАФАККУР УСЛУБИНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ- ФАЛСАФИЙ АҲАМИЯТИ

KALIT SO‘ZLAR:

тафаккур, фикр, мулоҳаза, ақлий билиш, структура, моҳият, борлиқ, табиат, жамият, мантиқ, менталитет, гносеология, селектив, вербал, башорат

ANNOTATSIYA

Бугунги кунда ер юзини қамраб олган глобаллашув жараёни натижасида инсоният онги ва тафаккурида кескин ўзгаришлар юз бермоқда. Айниқса, тафаккур тарзига турли хил ментал таъсирларнинг кучайиши ортмоқда. Дунёни англаш, ҳаёт ва жамият қонуниятларини ҳар томонлама идрок этиш, ер юзидаги турли халқлар ва миллатлар дунёқарашини билиш учун ҳам илмий тафаккурнинг аҳамияти беқиёс. Бир сўз билан айтганда, ёшларимизни илмий тафаккур билан қуроллантириш - давр талаби.

Falsafiy tafakkur uslubi, ilmiy tafakkur uslubi kabi, turli xil shakllarda namoyon bo'lish bilan xarakterlanadi. Bundan falsafiy tafakkur shakllarining ko'p qirraligi nimaga bog'liq degan savol, muqarrar, kelib chiqadi. Bu savolga javob berishda shu narsani hisobga olish kerakki, u yoki bu tafakkur uslubining mazmuni falsafaning asosiy masalasini, tafakkurning borliqqa, ruhning tabiatga bo'lgan munosabatini hal qilish bilan belgilanadigan dunyoqarashlik va metodologik xususiyati bilan belgilanadi. Agar dunyoqarashlik va metodologik jihatlar mazmuni belgilasa, ularning konkret namoyon bo'lishi esa falsafiy tafakkur uslubining shaklini tashkil etadi. Falsafiy tafakkur uslubi biluvchi subektning dunyoqarashlik va metodologik prinsiplar xarakteri bilan uzviy bog'langandir. Shuning uchun dunyoqarash va metodning o'zgarishi, tafakkur uslubining o'zgarishiga olib keladi. Binobarin, tafakkur uslubi shakllanish jarayonida metod va dunyoqarashga aks tasir etadi, ilmiy bilish sohasida u yoki bu vazifani hal qilish bilan bizning oldimizga yangi vazifalarni qo'yib, yangicha hal qilishga undaydi. Muayyan masala hal qilinishi bilan u yangi tafakkur jarayoniga tasir etadi. Shu o'rinda tafakkur uslubining ijodiylik, faollik xususiyati namoyon bo'ladi.

Tafakkur uslubi voqelikdagi narsa va hodisalarni, ularning rivojlanish qonuniyatlarini muayyan kishilarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, ehtiyojlari, manfaatlari ijtimoiy munosabatlariga muvofiq keladigan empirik bilimlar, ilmiy g'oyalar, nazariyalar, dunyoqarash va metodologik prinsiplarga muvofiq tarzda inikos etilishi va anglab olinish usulidir. Bu tarifda umuman barcha tafakkur uslubi shakllariga xos bo'lgan eng umumiy belgilar o'z aksini topgan. Tafakkur uslubining turli-tuman ko'rinishlari: birinchidan, atrofni o'rab turgan narsa va hodisalar hamda ularning rivojlanish qonuniyatlarining inson ongida to'la va chuqur inikos etilish darajasiga bog'liq. Bu esa, o'z navbatida tarixiy rivojlanishning turli bosqichlarida tafakkur anglab olishi lozim bo'lgan tushunchalar, tamoyillar, qonunlar sistemasiga bog'liq. Ikkinchidan, u jamiyatning ijtimoiy tuzilishi, milliy anana va urf-odatlar,

shaxsning individual ijodi, shuningdek, manaviy va boshqa ijtimoiy munosabatlarning majmui bilan taqozo etiladi.

Tafakkur uslubi insoniyatning ish uslubiga bevosita tasir qiladi. Muayyan ilmiy nazariya, metodologiya va dunyoqarash prinsiplariga suyangan tafakkurning aniq va ravshanligi amaliy faoliyatda bo'layotgan voqealarni muayyan nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilishga, ularning kelajakdagi rivojlanish tendensiyalari haqida xolisona xulosa chiqarishga, amaliyotda to'g'ri foydalanishga imkon tug'diradi.

Bunday tafakkur uslubi hozirgi istiqloq davrida ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy taraqqiyotning ilmiy asoslangan strategiya va taktikasini ishlab chiqishda katta ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

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